

Challenges That Facing Talented Students In Using Virtual Laboratories In Jordan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 17, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: November 21, 2020</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords: Challenges, Virtual Laboratories, Talented Students</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5904272</p>	<p><i>This study aimed to identify the challenges that facing talented students in using virtual laboratories in Jordan, the sample of the study consisted of (102) students, which were chosen intentionally from King Abdullah II schools for excellence in Mafraq during the second semester of the academic year 2019-2020. The descriptive and qualitative approach were used to answer research questions by using a three-part questionnaire (demographic data, challenges facing the use of virtual laboratories in King Abdullah II schools for excellence, and open-ended question for solutions to overcomes challenges that facing the use of virtual laboratories). Arithmetic averages, standard deviations, percentages, frequencies, and T-test were used for independent samples. The results showed that the degree of challenges that facing talented students in using virtual laboratories related to the whole dimensions of the questionnaire was an medium degree. In addition, the study showed that the degree of challenges of the virtual laboratory was high for both dimensions, the students and the quality of the software used, and it also appears that the degree of obstacles of the virtual laboratory was medium for the dimensions: the school environment, the curriculum and the teacher. Moreover. The study also identified the most important solutions to overcome the challenges that facing virtual laboratories in talented schools in Jordan.</i></p>

Introduction

The talented education is one of the most essential fields of special education which is witnessing rapid change and development due to economic transformations, cultural, political developments, and rapid technological progress. Jordan is considered one of the first Arab countries that pay attention and care for its talented and gifted students. A law is permitting to the Ministry of Education to establish educational institutions for talented and distinguished students by specifying its programs and other issues related to it, including the incentives of its employees (issued in paragraph (b) of the subject (41) and subject (45) of the Education Law No. (3) in year 1994. The establishment of schools for distinguished students comes as an initiative royal of His Majesty King Abdullah II Bin Al Hussein in the various governorates of the Kingdom to present an enriching educational style in educational environment and to prepare promising leaders in various disciplines. As the first school of King Abdullah II for Excellence was opened at the beginning of the 2001/2002 in Zarqa, and these schools continued to open in all governorates of the Kingdom. The number of schools at the beginning of the academic year 2019/2020 reached thirteen schools distributed over twelve governorates (Zarqa, Irbid, Salt, Aqaba, Tafila, Ajloun, Maan, Mafraq, Karak, Madaba, Jerash and two schools in the Capital, Amman). www.moe.gov.jo

The school's laboratory is one of the most prominent domains that help to raise the level of experiences of students in general and talented people in particular, and consolidate their scientific concepts, for example, Gunawan, G., et al. 2017, are revealing on the effect of the use of virtual labs on problem-solving ability of students to the concept of electricity. Some of the scientific research has proven that virtual laboratories, which are not a substitute for scientific laboratories and Virtual learning environment laboratories are artificial or imaginary real alternative to reality. It is known as virtual learning environment that aims to develop student's understanding and comprehension skills. Virtual laboratories must contain computers with high speed, storage capacity, appropriate scientific software, and communication with the global network. So that, the teacher can carry out scientific and digital experiments, repeat them, and see interactions and results without exposure to the lowest risks, least effort and cost possible (Zaytoun, 2005; Ahmed & Hasegawa 2014). However, the idea of applying virtual laboratories generally in regular schools and talented schools particularly faces set of obstacles and challenges such as the lack of tools and devices, the large number of students in the classroom, the large

number of classes that the teacher gives, and the lack of basic services in the virtual laboratory such as water, electricity, lack of safety and security requirements, and the limited space allocated to the laboratory, which hinders to conduct the experiments and poses a risk to students (Al-Zahrani, 2010; Ahmed, 2010; Al-Hazmi, 2010).

Virtual laboratories are virtual interactive environment that simulates real laboratories, enables the student to conduct remotely laboratory experiments on his own or on the group of individuals in different places, and they can participate in conducting the same experiment through the web or joint research project on a computer and access to conclusions in scientific. The virtual laboratories contain computers with high speed, storage capacity, appropriate scientific software and of communication with the global network that enables learners to carry out digital scientific experiments, repeat them, see interactions and results without exposure to the lowest risk, with the least effort and cost possible, and contribute significantly to deepening the understanding of difficult ideas (Zaytoun, 2005). In addition, it helps to bridge the deficit in laboratory equipment, and most course ideas can be covered with virtual experiences, which is impossible to achieve in reality, given to the limited of available practical time to the learner, and the number of laboratories inside the school. This will be done through the adoption of virtual laboratory technology that can simulate the processes, events, and experiences that occur in Real laboratories. Moreover, virtual laboratories are supporting to communicate and interact with others, it sometimes exceed real laboratories in some aspects (Noor, 2007). The virtual laboratories (Al-Shehri, 2009; Baraka, 2011; Al-Mousawi, 2012; Al-Hafiz, Ahmed, 2013) are distinguished by the following:

- The ability to transfer experiments and their results to the learner's educational electronic portfolio, which represents an effective means for a comprehensive evaluation of his performance.
- Improving researcher's performance as a result of saving travel time to research laboratories places and using them at any time or place at the lowest cost.
- The ability to cover all course ideas with interactive practical experiments and provide the highest rates of accuracy and safety in results.
- The possibility of performing laboratory experiments many times, especially those that are difficult to conduct in real laboratories because of their seriousness.
- The ease of investigating different virtual laboratories and studying their impact on the outputs of the experiment through virtual control panels.
- The user is not affected by the type of software or hardware used, as the programs used are valid for all systems.
- It delivers the content to the student and provides him/her with an ideal solution to carry out the experiments easily and easily.
- Ability to visualize data and phenomena that cannot be displayed through real experiments.
- The possibility of documenting the results of the experiments electronically in order to analyze, update or share them with others.
- The spread and globalization of virtual laboratories will help the emergence of criteria for scientific experimentation.
- Flexibility in conducting experiments and developing creative thinking and self-learning skills for the student.
- It compensates for the lack of the capacity of real laboratory for insufficient funding.
- The possibility of interaction and cooperation with others in conducting the same experiment from a distance.

Many research studies have shown the effectiveness of the virtual laboratory in academic achievement and the development of scientific skills in the subject of chemistry among first-year high school students (Hijazi, 2011). Another study showed that the virtual laboratories influence the achievement of physical concepts and the acquisition of higher thinking skills (Amal, 2010). Tracey's study (2007) and Marcel's study (2004) agree on the effectiveness of virtual laboratories in conducting virtual experiments via the Internet. Tracy's study was conducted in biology, whereas Marcel's study was conducted in chemistry. Shudayfat's study (2019) reached the importance and role of virtual universities in general and particularly in Jordan. This study focused on how to overcoming many challenges facing traditional universities such as financial problems, accessibility and the lack of faculty and other issues. Ngoyi identified several factors that play important role in virtual environment such as; insufficient preparation of teacher for virtual teaching, continuous technological changes and software problems, teacher's resistance to changes in their curricula, lack of communication between teachers and technology centers in schools, repeated failures of laboratory equipment and programs, students who were not actually able to study, and insufficient training to teach in Virtual environment (Ngoyi, 2013). In addition, Ngoyi outlined the proposed solutions to overcome these challenges, such as obtaining adequate funding, keeping them in the budget to train new and old teachers on using new educational programs, attending technology conferences and exhibitions, inviting software vendors to train teachers, providing appropriate and prompt technical support when teachers encounter technical problems may help to overcome specific

challenges, and collaborating with other teachers, who face similar problems, will be an excellent way to overcome challenges.

Problem of the Study

The problem is limited to answering the following questions:

- What are the challenges facing the use of virtual laboratories from the perspective of talented students in King Abdullah II Schools of Excellence?
- Is there a difference of the challenges facing talented students from using virtual laboratories in King Abdullah II Schools of Excellence related to the gender and classroom of the student?
- What are the proposed solutions to overcome the challenges facing from applying virtual laboratories in King Abdullah II schools for excellence from the perspective of talented students?

Significant of study:

- 1- Knowing the challenges of using virtual laboratories from the perspective of the talented.
- 2- Providing decision makers in the Ministry of Education with challenges in using virtual laboratories by talented students to develop a plan to overcome them.
- 3- Providing those in charge of King Abdullah II Schools with distinction and the challenges facing their students in using virtual laboratories.
- 4- Setting the proposed solutions to overcome the challenges facing from applying the virtual laboratories in King Abdullah II Schools of Excellence.

limitation of study

- The study was limited to the second semester of 2018/2019
- The study was applied to a sample of talented students in King Abdullah II Schools of Excellence in Al-Mafraq Governorate.
- The study was restricted to talented students in the secondary stage in King Abdullah Schools of Excellence in Al-Mafraq Governorate.

Procedures of Study

- The researchers reviewed the theoretical literature and previous studies regarding to the subject of the study, which is appropriate for one of the conference dimension (virtual laboratories).
- Tool of study was identified, modified, and extracted indications of validity and reliability.
- The researchers distributed the tool of study to the study's sample.
- Questionnaire was collected after applying it to the study's sample.
- Using excel spreadsheets, the data of study tool was unloaded and determined.
- SPSS program was used to extract arithmetic averages, standard deviations, and T-test for independent samples, percentages, and repetitions to answer study questions.

Methodology

Study Approach: To answer the research questions, the researchers used the descriptive approach by developing a questionnaire about the challenges facing the use of virtual laboratories in King Abdullah II schools for excellence in Jordan. They also used a qualitative (qualitative) approach through open-ended questions (one question only). As the analyzing of the answers to the question, it aims to reach the concepts and relationships that can explain the collected data by visualizing the previously collected answers, and organizing them in a logical way (repetitions and percentages) to explain and clarify solutions to overcome the challenges facing talented students in using Virtual laboratories.

sample of Study : The sample of the study included all talented students from the tenth grade to the twelfth grade in King Abdullah II School for Excellence at the second semester 2019-2020 in Al-Mafraq. The numbers of students were 102 (male and female). As distributed by classroom as 55 students from the eleventh grade, 47 students from the twelfth grade. Whereas, they distributed by gender as follows 42 males, 60 females.

Tool of Study: The questionnaire is adapted from Al-Juhani (2014) and Ngoyi (2013) to answer the study questions. Where the questionnaire consists of three parts:

- Part one: general information about students (gender and classroom).
- Part two: It included 35 phrases and was divided into five areas as follows:
 - first area: Challenges related to the school environment and consists of 7 items.
 - second area: teacher-related challenges and consists of 7 items.
 - third area: the challenges related to the student and it consists of 7 items.
 - fourth area: Challenges related to the curriculum and consists of 7 items.
 - Fifth area: Challenges related to the type of software which consists of 7 items.

- Part Three: Includes an open question that includes the student's answer to a question : What are the proposed solutions to overcome the challenges facing from applying virtual laboratories in King Abdullah II Schools of Excellence?

Validity of Tool :The instrument validity was verified by presenting it to a group of experts with experience and specialization in special education. Ten experts were chosen from different Jordanian universities by taking their suggestions, observations, and making the necessary modifications as follows:

- Linguistic reformulate of some paragraphs
- Merge duplicated paragraphs and reformulate them appropriately .

Reliability of Tool

Reliability of instrument was confirmed by calculating the internal Reliability of the paragraphs according to the Cronbach's alpha coefficient, and Table (1) shows the results of the reliability.

Table (1): Internal Consistency of the paragraphs in study tool's

<i>NO.</i>	<i>Areas</i>	<i>Internal Consistency</i>
<i>1</i>	<i>Challenges related to the school environment</i>	0.89
<i>2</i>	<i>Challenges related to teacher</i>	0.92
<i>3</i>	<i>Challenges related to the student</i>	0.90
<i>4</i>	<i>Challenges related to the curriculum</i>	0.88
<i>5</i>	<i>Challenges related to the type of software used</i>	0.85

Table (1) shows that the internal Reliability of paragraphs in study tool's that describes the study Reliability. In order to answer the study tool, the five-core Likert scale was adopted for the responses of the paragraphs (very high, high, medium, low, and very low). They are represented (5, 4, 3, 2, 1) respectively. The scale categories were calculated through the use of following equation: (the upper limit of the scale (5) - the lower limit of the scale (1)) ÷ number of categories required (3). $(5-1) \div 3 = 1.33$ Then add the answer (1.33) to the end of each category. The results are as follows:

From 1.00 -2.33	low
From 2.34-3.67	medium
From 3.68-5.00	high

Results

Results of the first question: What are the challenges facing using of the virtual laboratories from the perspective of talented students in King Abdullah II Schools of Excellence? Mathematical averages and standard deviations were calculated for the degree of challenges facing from the applying of virtual laboratories in King Abdullah II schools for excellence from the viewpoint of talented students, as in Table No. (2).

Table (2) Mathematical Averages and Standard Deviations for the Degree of Challenges from applying the Virtual Lab in King Abdullah II Schools for Excellence from the Viewpoint of Talented Students

<i>Dimension</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
<i>Student</i>	102	3.81	0.54	High
<i>Software</i>	102	3.73	0.69	High
<i>Environment</i>	102	3.59	0.82	Moderate
<i>Curriculum</i>	102	3.47	0.77	Moderate
<i>Teacher</i>	102	3.38	0.64	Moderate
<i>Total</i>	102	3.60	.45	Moderate

Table (2) shows that the degree of challenges facing from applying the virtual laboratories on both dimensions; the students and the type of software used came at a high level with average 3.81 and 3.73 respectively. Whereas, the dimensions related to the school environment, the curriculum, and the teacher came in a medium degree with average (3.59), (3.47) and (3.88), respectively. It also shows that the degree of challenges facing from applying the virtual laboratories as whole came with average degree and score (3.60).

Results of the second question: Is there a difference in the challenges facing talented students in using virtual laboratories in King Abdullah II schools for excellence due to the gender and classroom of the student? The arithmetic averages and standard deviations were calculated as in Table (3) and Table (4).

Table (3) Mathematical Averages for Virtual Lab Obstacles by Student's Gender

Dimension	Sex	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Environment	Male	42	3.61	0.86	0.23
	Female	60	3.57	0.81	0.19
Teacher	Male	42	3.39	0.67	0.18
	Female	60	3.38	0.63	0.15
Student	Male	42	3.83	0.51	0.14
	Female	60	3.80	0.57	0.13
Curriculum	Male	42	3.34	0.81	0.22
	Female	60	3.57	0.75	0.17
Software	Male	42	3.66	0.67	0.18
	Female	60	3.77	0.72	0.17
Total	Male	42	3.57	0.44	0.12
	Female	60	3.62	0.47	0.11

Table (4) Mathematical Averages for Virtual Lab Obstacles by Student's Classroom

Dimension	Grade	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Environment	11	57	3.62	0.86	0.19
	12	45	3.54	0.78	0.22
Teacher	11	57	3.56	0.56	0.45
	12	45	3.10	0.67	0.18
Student	11	57	3.94	0.55	0.12
	12	45	3.62	0.47	0.45
Curriculum	11	57	3.58	0.82	0.18
	12	45	3.31	0.68	0.19
Software	11	57	3.88	0.74	0.17
	12	45	3.49	0.55	0.15
Total	11	57	3.72	0.47	0.11
	12	45	3.41	0.37	0.10

Table (3) and Table (4), there are apparent differences in arithmetic averages between male students, female students, and the student in classroom in the challenges facing talented students of using virtual laboratories in King Abdullah II schools. To find out the effect of apparent differences, the T-test was used for independent samples between males and females and between the eleventh and twelfth grades, as in Table (5) and Table (6):

Table (5) T-test for independent difference groups between male and female

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means		
		F	Sig.	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Environment	Equal variances assumed	0.04	0.84	0.14	31.00	0.89
	Equal variances not assumed			0.14	27.10	0.89
Teacher	Equal variances assumed	0.04	0.85	0.05	31.00	0.96
	Equal variances not assumed			0.05	27.17	0.96
Student	Equal variances assumed	0.14	0.72	0.15	31.00	0.88
	Equal variances not assumed			0.16	29.61	0.88
Curriculum	Equal variances assumed	0.20	0.66	-0.86	31.00	0.40
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.85	26.89	0.40
Software	Equal variances assumed	0.03	0.86	-0.45	31.00	0.65
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.46	29.30	0.65
Total	Equal variances assumed	0.05	0.82	-0.102	31.00	0.75
	Equal variances not assumed			-0.102	29.06	0.75

Table(6) T-test for independent difference groups between the first and second secondary grade

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means		
Dimension		F	Sig.	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)

Environment	Equal variances assumed	.126	0.73	0.28	31.00	0.78
	Equal variances not assumed			0.29	27.66	0.78
Teacher	Equal variances assumed	.038	0.85	2.16	31.00	0.04
	Equal variances not assumed			2.08	22.65	0.05
Student	Equal variances assumed	2.056	0.16	1.72	31.00	0.10
	Equal variances not assumed			1.79	28.73	0.09
Curriculum	Equal variances assumed	1.062	0.31	0.99	31.00	0.102
	Equal variances not assumed			1.03	29.01	0.31
Software	Equal variances assumed	.877	0.36	1.60	31.00	0.12
	Equal variances not assumed			1.71	30.35	0.10
Total	Equal variances assumed	.658	0.42	1.97	31.00	0.06
	Equal variances not assumed			2.07	29.66	0.05

Tables (5) and Table (6), the T-test values shown that there are no statistical significance in determining the degree of challenges facing from applying virtual laboratories in King Abdullah II schools for excellence from the viewpoint of talented students due to the student's gender or class.

Results of the third question: What are the proposed solutions to overcome the challenges facing from applying the virtual laboratories in King Abdullah II schools for excellence from the viewpoint of talented students? The qualitative approach was used by analyzing the 102 students answer's manually to the open question to extract solutions from the students' answers and determining their repetitions and percentages as in Table (7).

Table (7) The proposed solutions to overcome the challenges facing from applying the virtual laboratories in King Abdullah II schools for excellence from the viewpoint of talented students

No.	The Proposed Solutions	Repetitions	Percentage
1	Providing a virtual laboratory in the school	80	%78
2	Conducting training sessions for teachers on how to use virtual laboratories	72	%71
3	Conducting training sessions for students on how to use virtual laboratories	65	%64
4	Including curricula with goals to be achieved through virtual laboratories	53	%52
5	Providing specialists in the applying of virtual laboratories	48	%47
6	Provide samples showing the effectiveness of virtual laboratories in the educational process.	36	%35
7	Providing educational material for teachers and students explaining the concept of virtual laboratories, their features and benefits.	25	%25
8	Training teachers and students on some software used in virtual laboratories	23	%23
9	Providing network of communications and services of its own to operate virtual laboratories through it	15	%15

Table (7) shows that the most proposed solutions suggested by talented students to overcome the challenges facing from applying virtual laboratories.

Discussion

The result of the first question can be explained by the fact that there are challenges facing from applying virtual laboratories in terms of; the lack of virtual laboratories in the school, lack of computers, Internet service, data display devices, and specialists in virtual laboratories, lack of teachers and students in the use of computers, lack of training programs on the use of virtual laboratories, lack of electronic links to virtual experiences, lack of multiple copies of software in schools, and lack of design of interesting software and difficulty in using the software. These result are also consistent with a reference to both (Al-Zahrani, 2010; Ahmed, 2008; Al-Hazem J, 2010) in identifying the challenges facing from applying virtual laboratories in schools. In addition, Reda(2010) added the importance of virtual laboratories in developing scientific thinking). Also several studies indicated to a set of experiences in developed countries in using and activation of virtual laboratories, such as (Baraka, 2010), (Radi, 2008) and (Al-Baltan, 2012).

The result of the second question can be explained as whatever the student's gender or classroom, they agree on the challenges facing from applying virtual laboratories in their schools, which were mentioned in the first question of the study. Some references also support the agreement of talented students in the challenges that facing the use of virtual laboratories in education. Some of them pointed to the weak infrastructure in Jordan for communication and Internet problems (speed, lack of coverage for most regions of the Jordan) in addition to the

lack of social acceptance of the quality of teaching in this way (Al-Dahshan, 2007). Some also pointed to the traditional educational mentality in education, and doubts about the achievement level of students studying in this way (18), N.J(2005). Some mentioned to the high cost of technical devices in terms of their ownership and periodic maintenance. also the need for teachers to have many technical courses in the absence of a lack of technical support to practice this method of education, Vince(2004). Also The third question indicated to solutions suggested by talented students to overcome the challenges facing from applying virtual laboratories that starts by the availability of virtual laboratory in their schools (78%), and then with other solutions such as holding training courses for teachers and students on how the use of virtual laboratories, the inclusion of curricula with lessons that are implemented through virtual laboratories, as well as preparing the school environment for the applying of virtual laboratories from computers, the Internet, maintenance and software specialists.

Conclusions

The results of the study showed that there are challenges facing from applying the virtual laboratories in talented schools in Jordan represented in students, the software used, the school environment, the curriculum, and the teacher. The study also identified the most important solutions to overcome the challenges facing from applying virtual laboratories in schools such as preparing a virtual laboratory and then taking solutions that was indicated in the results of the third question of the study. Therefore, the researchers believe that if the following were taken:

- Providing decision makers in the Ministry of Education with the challenges of teaching virtual laboratories in talented schools .
- Develop a strategic plan to overcome the challenges of teaching virtual laboratories in talented schools.
- Holding courses and training programs for teachers and students to enable them to overcome the challenges they face in using the virtual laboratory.

We will be able to apply the virtual laboratories in talented schools, which in turn enable talented students to benefit from the importance of virtual laboratories referred to (Al-Shehri, 2009; Baraka, 2011; Iman, 2011; Al-Musawi, 2012; Al-Hafiz, Ahmed, 2013) in theoretical literature and previous studies.

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